

THE WAYS TO DEVELOP SPEAKING SKILLS OF ESL LEARNERS

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Abstract: The ever –growing necessity for good communication skills in English has created an immense demand for English teaching all over the world. These days, a great deal of people want to be expert in English. A number of methods and approaches have been suggested and implemented to practice in the domain of teaching English, specifically teaching speaking skills to students who speak other languages. Yet, new ways are being researched and experimented in the lessons as technology is being advanced and making the process more engaging, easier and interesting in this realm. Analysis of assessing speaking skills and ways to improve this ability of second language learners will be discussed in this article.

Key words: Speaking skills, testing, useful techniques, questions, style of speech, candidates, interactive communication, pictures, role play, pronunciation, the accurate measurement.

Setting and marking a written test of grammar or reading is relatively easy to organize and time-effective. A test of speaking, conversely, is quite complicated process. If all the students of a class have to be interviewed individually, the disruption caused, and the time taken, may seem to outweigh the benefits. Furthermore, every tester may have their own way of assessment criteria for judging speaking, differences that are less acute when it comes to judging writing or grammar knowledge, for instance.

A decent speaker of English should be able to do the following speaking tasks at least: providing personal information, describing sequence of events, giving instructions, making comparisons where relevant, giving explanations, expressing need or requirements, asking for help, seeking permission, expressing and justifying opinions, complaining and etc.

As Hughes (2000) considers, the most common format for the testing of oral interaction is the interview. In its traditional form, however, it has at least one potentially serious drawback. The relationship between the tester and the candidate is usually such that the candidate speaks as to a superior and is unwilling to take the initiative. As a result, only one style of speech is elicited, and many functions (such as asking for information) are not represented in the candidate’s performance.

There are several useful techniques to improve the students’ speaking skills:

1. Questions and requests for information

Yes/No questions should generally be avoided, except perhaps at the very beginning of the interview, while the candidate is still warming up. Performance of various operations (of the kind listed in the two sets of specifications above) can be elicited through requests of the kind:

‘Can you describe me how/why...?’ and

‘Can you express what you think of ...?’

2. Pictures

Describing a set of pictures as well can show the levels of the students’ speaking.

3. Role play

Candidates can be asked to assume a role in a particular situation. This allows the ready elicitation of other language functions.

4. Reading aloud

Ability to read aloud may as well assess how students pronounce words in English. Though, interference between the reading and the speaking skills was inevitable. But, if that ability is needed or its development has been a course objective, use of the method may be acceptable.

5. Narrative stories

Tooth and Renshaw (2009) echoed what Coles (2010) has advocated for years, that narrative stories increase the power of learning fundamental to human capacities, commitments, communication, and cultural histories. Narrative in pedagogy elicits attention, responses, and reflection. Dervin (2009) explored stories that inhibit cross

cultural learning, myths from study abroad programs. When people make claims and tell stories, they provide their interpretation of experiences and events. What stories form the cultural myths? How can one learn the amount of eye contact, touch, or proximity acceptable in a foreign culture? Does the community value diversity? the concept of a cross-cultural teacher understanding the varied implications for the internationalization of English will lead individuals engaged in cross-cultural teaching to value each situation uniquely.

Put candidates at their ease so that they can show what they are capable of. Individual oral tests will always be particularly stressful for candidates. It is important to be pleasant and reassuring throughout, showing interest in what the candidate says through both verbal and non-verbal signals. It is especially important to make the initial stages of the test well within the capacities of all reasonable candidates. Interviews, for example, can begin with straightforward requests for personal (but not too personal) details, remarks about the weather, and so on. Testers should avoid constantly reminding candidates that they are being assessed. In particular they should not be seen to make notes on the candidates' performance during the interview or other activity. For the same reason, transitions between topics and between techniques should be made as natural as possible. The interview should be ended at a level at which the candidate clearly feels comfortable, thus leaving him or her with a sense of accomplishment.

The accurate measurement of oral ability is not easy. It takes considerable time and effort, including training, to obtain valid and reliable results. Nevertheless, where a test is high stakes, or backwash is an important consideration, the investment of such time and effort may be considered necessary. Readers are reminded that the appropriateness of content, of rating scales levels, and of elicitation techniques used in oral testing will depend upon the needs of individual institutions or organizations.

There are four categories which should be assessed during the speaking exams. These are: Grammar and Vocabulary, Discourse Management, Pronunciation and Interactive communication. On the scale of Grammar and Vocabulary, candidates are awarded marks for the accurate and appropriate use of syntactic forms and

vocabulary in order to meet the task requirements at each level. The range and appropriate use of vocabulary are also assessed here. On the scale of Discourse Management, examiner is looking for evidence of the candidate's ability to express ideas and opinions in coherent, connected speech. The candidate's ability to maintain a coherent flow of language with an appropriate range of linguistic recourses over several utterances is assessed here.

Pronunciation refers to the candidate's ability to produce comprehensible utterances to fulfill the task requirements, i.e. it refers to the production of individual sounds, the appropriate linking of words, and the use of stress and intonation to convey the intended meaning.

Interactive Communication refers to the candidate's ability to interact with the interlocutor and the other candidate by initiating and responding appropriately and at the required speed and rhythm to fulfill the task requirements. It includes the ability to use functional language and strategies to maintain or repair interaction, e.g. in conversational turn-taking, and a willingness to develop the conversation and move the task towards a conclusion. Candidates should be able to maintain the coherence of the discussion and may, if necessary, ask the interlocutor or the other candidate for clarification.

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